

Membrane electrode for the selective determination of iridium(III)

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Abstract : The iridium(III) membrane electrode prepared depends on the use of calix[6]arene with dioctyl phthalate (DOP), didecyl phthalate (DDP) and nitrophenyloctylether (NPOE) as a plasticize materials with PVC membranes. The electrode containing (DDP) gives linear potentiometric response towards iridium(III) ions over the concentration range 1×10^{-7} – 1×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹ with a Nernstian slope of 22.05 mV decade⁻¹ and lower limit of detection of 1×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ Ir^{III} ions over the pH range of 6–10. The electrode shows high selectivity for Ir^{III} when mixed with different varieties of alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal cations. The electrode shows long life span, high reproducibility, fast response and long term stability. The lower limit of detection, lower limit of linear range, accuracy, precision and sensitivity were measured. The obtained results reveal good characteristics of the proposed electrode.

Keywords : Iridium, sensor for iridium, determination of iridium, membrane electrode, didecylephthalate.

Introduction

Iridium is a very hard brittle silvery white transition metal. It is found in gravel deposits with platinum ores. It represents 3×10^{-6} ppm from earth's crust. It is used in tip gold pin points, crucibles and heat resistant alloys. It is also used in cancer irradiation, hypodermic needles and as a hardening agent for platinum¹. There are many methods for determination of iridium which are expensive and need long time and pretreatment procedures. However, ion-selective electrode method proves to be convenient, low cost, simple, selective, and easy without any sample pretreatment or derivation. Some different methods for the determination of iridium were used. Coulometric methods²⁻⁴, catalytic method⁵, voltammetric method⁶, spectrofluorimetric method⁷, spectrophotometric methods⁸⁻¹⁰, luminescence method¹¹, radiometric method¹², atomic absorption spectrometric method^{13,14}, adsorptiometric method^{15,16}, ICP method¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and thermal ionization mass spectrometric method²⁰. In the last few decades potentiometric membrane sensors for determination of many cations such as Sr and Cr^{III}, received much attention. Many compounds have been suggested as electro-active materials such as a modified calix[6]arene, Schiff base complexes^{21,22}, and ISE methods for determination of neodymium(III) and promethium were devel-

oped^{23,24}. In this work, the iridium(III) electrode depending on calix[6]arene with didecylephthalate (DDP) in plasticized PVC membranes is described. The electrode shows high sensitivity, long-term stability and good selectivity for Ir^{III} ions over many common ions. The proposed sensor is successfully used for the determination of Ir^{III} ions in synthetic samples.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions :

All the reagents used were of analytical grade and doubly distilled water were used. Didecylephthalate (DDP), dioctylephthalate (DOP), nitrophenyl octyle ether (NPOE) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Company (Milwaukee, USA). Calix[6]arene derivative namely : 37-[(diethoxythiophosphoryl)oxyl]-5,11,17,23,29,35-hexakis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-calix[6]arene-38,39,40,41,42-phenol (CX); was synthesized according to a previous procedure²⁵. Fig. 1 shows the calix[6]arene structure. Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) (Fluka) and one gram of standard hydrated IrCl₃ (Winlab, UK) was used. Solutions of iridium ions (1×10^{-2} – 1×10^{-7}) were prepared by dilutions. Stock solutions of metal ions were also prepared and diluted as suitable. Dilute solution of NaOH and HCl were used for adjusting the pH.

[R1 : OP (=S) (OEt)2]; [R2-R6 : OH]

Thio-phosphorylated calix[6]arene derivatives

Fig. 1. Calix[6]arene structure.

Apparatus :

Digital pH-meter (Schott. Gerate, D62381, Germany) using iridium(III) potentiometric sensor in conjunction with on EIL-types RJ23 calomel reference electrode. A glass Ag-AgCl combination electrode (Consort, 5210B BBS) was used. The internal filling solution of the sensor was $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ iridium(III) chloride solution. Unicam model (PU4100) atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used for determination of iridium.

Iridium(III) potentiometric sensor measurements :

The membrane composed of 2 mg calix[6]arene, 60 mg PVC and either 120 mg (DOP) or 120 mg (DDP) or 120 mg (NPOE) for Ia, Ib and Ic, respectively. These components were dissolved in distilled (THF) and transferred to glass rings of 24 mm i.d. resting on a glass plate after solvent evaporation, the obtained membrane was cut out into disks of 7 mm i.d. The membrane disks were mounted in electrode bodies (Type IS561, Philips, Endhoven and Nertherlands) for potentiometric measurements. After electrode adjustments, it was soaked for 24 h in 10^{-2} M solution of IrCl_3 . The electrode body was filled with the inner solution [IrCl_3 10^{-3} M + KCl 10^{-3} M]. The cell potential was recorded corresponding to each Ir^{3+} concentration. A calibration graph can be constructed for the cell potential versus $-\log [\text{Ir}^{3+}]$. The following cell assembly was applied.

Calomel reference electrode//sample solution//membrane/inner filling solution/Ag/AgCl :

The potentiometric selectivity coefficient ($K^{\text{Pot}}_{\text{Ir}^{3+}, \text{J}^{z+}}$) values for different common cations were obtained by the

separate solution method (10^{-3} M solution for both iridium and interferent)²⁶. The pH adjustments of the tested solutions to the electrode optimum pH value were achieved by using 0.1 M NaOH or 0.1 M HCl.

Determination of iridium by flame AAS :

Iridium(III) was determined from a binary mixture with sodium in chloride solution. Suitable atomic absorption conditions for iridium measurement were achieved at wave length (208.9) nm and with an air-acetylene.

Determination of iridium(III) by ISE :

Suitable sample solution was transferred to a 100 ml beaker then it was adjusted to the optimum pH range from⁶⁻¹⁰. The electrode in conjunction with the reference electrode was applied into the sample solution. The potential reading of the resulting solution was referred to previously prepared calibration graph for iridium. The obtained results were compared with those given by air acetylene flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

Results and discussion

Effect of composition :

Three membrane compositions were tried to determine iridium(III) cation. They were based on the use of different plasticizers DOP (Ia), DDP (Ib) and NPOE (Ic). The electrodes with membrane types Ia and Ib showed slopes 24.2 mV and 22.05 mV and showed linear ranges 10^{-3} – 10^{-2} M , 10^{-4} – 10^{-2} M . They showed detection limit values $6.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $1.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, respectively. The second membrane Ib gave the best performance and the best Nernstian behavior. In contrast to the Ia and Ib; it was found that the membrane Ic did not have any Nernstian behavior (Fig. 2) shows the calibration curve of the membranes Ia and Ib. Table 1 shows the potentiometric response characteristics of Ir^{III} sensor. The response mechanism of this electrode can be written as the following equations.

m = membrane site, s = solution site

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the potentiometric response of the sensor was studied using $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ IrCl_3 solutions. The pH was adjusted by

Fig. 2. Calibration graphs for electrodes with membrane types Ia, Ib : (▲) Ib, (■) Ia.

values by increasing pH value is explained due to formation of Ir_2O_3 ²⁷ as shown in the following reaction.

Response time :

The potential-time curves of the Ib electrode at different concentrations of IrCl_3 solution are shown in Fig. 4. The response time is defined as the time which elapses between the instant when an ion-selective electrode and a reference electrode (ISE cell) are brought into contact with a sample solution (or at which the activity of the ion of interest in a solution is changed) and the first instant at which the emf/time slope ($\Delta E/\Delta t$) becomes equal to a limiting value selected on the basis of the experimental conditions and/or requirements concerning the accuracy (e.g. 0.6 mV/min)²⁸. After calculation of the response time for different Ir^{3+} concentrations in the range

Table 1. Response characterization of iridium electrodes based on different plasticizers

Electrode type	Plasticizers	Slope (mv/decade)	Linear range (M)	Detection limit (M)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)
Ia	DOP	24.2	10^{-3} - 10^{-2}	6.3×10^{-5}	0.9983
Ib	DDP	22.05	10^{-4} - 10^{-2}	1.6×10^{-4}	0.9934

addition of dilute hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide as suitable. From pH-potential profiles Fig. 3, it is clear that the potential reading for the membrane sensor are constant over the pH ranges 8-10, 8-10 and 6-10, respectively. These are the useful pH range over which sensor can be used. A change in potential values below pH 5 and below pH 4 for Ir^{3+} concentration of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ was observed. Generally, the lowering in potential

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on performance of electrode with membrane type Ib : (▲) 0.01 M IrCl_3 , (■) 0.001 M IrCl_3 .

Fig. 4. Dynamic response of iridium selection electrode based on calix[6]arene with (DDP) as plasticizer (Ib) type : (*) mV 10^{-4} M , (■) mV 10^{-3} M , (▲) mV 10^{-2} M .

(10^{-4} - 10^{-2} M), it was found that the response time of the electrode was 2 s. The short response time reflects the fast measurement procedure.

Electrode selectivity :

Table 2 shows the selectivity coefficient for the Ib electrode. The selectivity coefficient values are the best for monovalent cations reaching -4.59 , -4.27 , -4.22 ,

Table 2. Selectivity coefficient values ($\log(K^{\text{Pot}}_{\text{Ir}^{3+}, \text{J}^{z+}})$) of iridium selective electrode incorporating membrane based on (DDP)

Sl. No.	Interferent	Ionic radius (Å)	$-\log(K^{\text{Pot}}_{\text{Ir}^{3+}, \text{J}^{z+}})$
1.	Ag ⁺	0.72	4.59
2.	Ca ²⁺	0.99	1.36
3.	Na ⁺	0.97	4.27
4.	Cd ²⁺	0.97	0.92
5.	Pb ²⁺	1.19	1.05
6.	NH ₄ ⁺	1.43	4.22
7.	Hg ²⁺	1.10	0.66
8.	Fe ³⁺	0.64	1.10
9.	K ⁺	1.33	3.24
10.	Ni ²⁺	0.69	1.49
11.	Co ²⁺	0.72	1.20

-3.24 for Ag⁺, Na⁺, NH₄⁺, K⁺, respectively. Divalent cations showed selectivity coefficient values higher than monovalent cations reaching -1.05, -1.49, -1.20 for Pb²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ respectively. This means that the electrode is more selective towards monovalent cations than divalent. The highest selectivity coefficient values were recorded for Cd²⁺ and Hg²⁺ (-0.92 and -0.66), which means that care should be taken for measurements in presence of both cations. By studying the values of ionic radius of the studied cations it is found that there is a relation between the selectivity coefficient value and the ionic radius.

Effect of soaking :

The electrode with membrane type Ib was chosen to perform the effect of soaking on the electrode performance. Table 3 shows the obtained results. It is found that, the electrode showed perfect Nernstian behaviors for long time. The membrane was soaked continuously

Table 3. Effect of soaking time in 10⁻² M IrCl₃ on the performance of Ib type electrode (DDP)

Soaking time (day)	Slope (mV/decade)	Linear range (M)	Correlation coefficient (R^2)
1	16.04	10 ⁻⁴ -10 ⁻¹	0.9880
2	17.24	10 ⁻⁶ -10 ⁻¹	0.9820
3	22.05	10 ⁻⁴ -10 ⁻¹	0.9930
5	17.85	10 ⁻⁴ -10 ⁻¹	0.9790
11	15.57	10 ⁻³ -10 ⁻¹	0.9870
30	16.00	10 ⁻³ -10 ⁻¹	0.9740

30 days in 10⁻² M IrCl₃. After 2 days the slope reaches 17.24 mV/decade but after 3 days the slope reaches 22.05 mV/decade. Practically, the electrode was working within Nernstian response (16 mV/decade) up to one month. The linear range changes by prolonged soaking in 10⁻³ M IrCl₃ solution. After 5 days the lower limit of linear range become higher (10⁻⁴ M). Then after 11 days it reached 10⁻³. The changes in the lower limit of linear range for Ir electrode with prolonged soaking is explained due to leaching out of the sensing membrane component.

Analytical application :

Iridium sensor (Ib) was successfully used for direct determination of iridium(III) in binary mixture of 10⁻³ M (Ir³⁺ + Na⁺). The results were compared with those obtained from atomic absorption spectrometry. Table 4 shows a good agreement between both data. The RSD values of the present electrode method (0.22-0.99) were close to those of AAS (0.18-0.74) when analyzing samples (19-2.89 ppm).

Table 4. Determination of iridium in binary mixture using iridium electrode type Ib compared with atomic absorption spectrometry

Sample No.	AAS method (conc. ppm)	RSD (%)	ISE method (conc. ppm)	RSD (%)
1.	19.00	0.29	18.80	0.53
2.	9.40	0.18	9.28	0.22
3.	2.89	0.47	2.81	0.99

Conclusion

The proposed iridium(III) sensor based on phosphorylated calix[6]arene derivative is introduced here as the first iridium selective electrode. The electrode gave high selectivity towards most of the tested common cations. Practically, the electrode can be applied for determination of Ir³⁺ down to detection limit 6.3 × 10⁻⁵ M. The electrode fast response (2 s) is advantageous over other different methods. The wide working pH range enables the analytical chemist to use the electrode for many applications.

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